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Optimization and Construction of Team Cooperation Mechanism in Teacher Management

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Abstract

This study aims to optimize and construct team cooperation mechanisms in teacher management, with a focus on teachers at Jinan Vocational College. Utilizing both qualitative and quantitative research methods, the study employed surveys, in-depth interviews, and case analyses, surveying 100 teachers to explore the impact of team cooperation on work efficiency, teaching effectiveness, and job satisfaction.

Initially, a survey was conducted to gather data on teachers' satisfaction with existing management mechanisms and their needs for team cooperation. This was followed by in-depth interviews with 20 teachers to gain insights into their experiences and challenges related to team cooperation in practice. Finally, successful case studies were analyzed to examine the effects of various team cooperation mechanisms on optimizing teacher management.

The results indicate that constructing effective team cooperation mechanisms can significantly enhance teachers' collaborative abilities, innovation capacity, and teaching quality. Based on these findings, the study proposes a framework for optimizing team cooperation mechanisms, including aspects such as role allocation, communication strategies, and incentive systems. This framework provides theoretical support and practical recommendations for teacher management in vocational institutions.

Keywords: Team Cooperation Mechanisms, Teacher Management, Vocational Education, Teaching Effectiveness, Mechanism Optimization

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